

METHODS OF IMPLEMENTING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada ta'limda raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida nimalarga erishish mumkinligi aytilgan va ayrim tatbiq etishning shakllarga tuxtalgan. Jumladan interaktiv dars usullari, raqamli ta'lim platformalari, virtual ta'lim muassasalari, tajribaviy o'qitish, individual o'qitish kabi shakllar ko'rsatib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: interaktiv, dars, usul, raqamli, ta'lim platformalari, virtual ta'lim, , tajribaviy o'qitish, individual, motivatsiya.

Annotatsiya: This article tells what can be achieved with the help of digital technologies in education and touches on some forms of implementation. Among them, forms such as interactive teaching methods, digital educational platforms, virtual educational institutions, experiential teaching, and individual teaching are shown.

Key words: interactive, lesson, method, digital, educational platforms, virtual education, experiential learning, individual, motivation.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассказывается, чего можно достичь с помощью цифровых технологий в образовании, и затрагиваются некоторые формы реализации. Среди них показаны такие формы, как интерактивные методы обучения, цифровые образовательные платформы, виртуальные образовательные учреждения, экспериментальное обучение и индивидуальное обучение.

Ключевые слова: интерактив, урок, метод, цифровые, образовательные платформы, виртуальное образование, экспериментальное обучение, личность, мотивация.

The decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan" for 2022-2026, which includes the priority section for the development of the field of education and science, was approved. The inclusion of this section in the decree of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan demonstrates the importance of the task of developing new educational technologies. It should be said that this development strategy is directly related to our educational program. [1].

The following forms can be used as an example of the forms of application of digital technologies in education, and they differ in their use. let's take a look at them.

Interactive teaching methods: Digital technologies allow students to actively participate in their learning process through interactive teaching methods. For example, through interactive learning programs, online classes, and interactive course materials, students can improve their participation and learning.

Digital Learning Platforms: Digital learning platforms are external platforms or software for managing the learning process and providing information to students. These platforms provide students with course materials, assignments, and practice exercises, as well as promote communication between teachers and students.

Virtual educational institutions: Digital technologies allow students to control the learning process through virtual educational institutions. Virtual educational institutions, using virtual reality (VR) and simulation technologies, allow students to study in virtual hotels, laboratories, or institutions with a staff consultant.

Experiential learning: Digital technologies are also used to enhance experiential learning and hands-on learning. In this form, through virtual laboratories, simulation programs, and other technological tools, students learn practical exercises and experiments.

Individualized Learning: Digital technologies allow students to create and manage their own learning paths. Personalization is used to develop and provide personalized learning opportunities based on student information and learning.

These forms are widely used methods for learning, implementing, and improving educational effectiveness of digital technologies in education. Digital technologies have played a major role in making the education sector more innovative and interactive.

In conclusion, Digital technologies enable the creation of an advanced environment for students to participate in lessons and tasks, learn and absorb information. These technologies have played an important role in increasing students' interest, learning motivation and involvement in the educational process.

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